

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Rachmawati, I., Ardhanariswari, K. A., & Hendariningrum, R. (2024). Cultural Heritage in Sustainable Tourism. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 7(4), 63-77.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.07.04.525

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Cultural Heritage in Sustainable Tourism

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the influence of sustainable tourism on cultural heritage in the last seven years, namely 2018 to 2024. This research uses qualitative methods with a literature study approach. Research data was obtained from the Scopus database of 335 articles, proceedings, and book chapters. Data analysis in this research used VOSviewer and NVivo 14 tools. The results of the 335 article documents showed that Italy had the most considerable contribution to the document, and Aristotle University of Thessaloniki had the most enormous contribution. Sustainable development of industrial heritage tourism A case study of the Industrial Monuments Route in Poland by Szromek et al. (2021) became the most popular article with 41 citations. This research shows that the tourism industry's impact on cultural heritage is only sometimes positive. Excessive tourism can damage cultural heritage. Sustainable tourism aims to balance economic growth with cultural preservation and environmental management. Community participation is essential to achieving this goal, and research on this is relatively new. This research is limited by secondary data, which continues to increase and change. Therefore, it is essential to maintain research and create better data filtering.

Keywords: Cultural Heritage, Sustainable Tourism, Cultural Preservation, Bibliometric, Community Participation

1. Introduction

Referring to the ForwardKey Report, the most visited cities throughout 2022 are Antalya, San Jose Calbo, Puerto Vallarta, Punta Cana, and San Salvador (ForwardKeys, 2022). These cities are cities with beach tourism and other natural resources. Although cities like Antalya also offer cultural heritage tourism, this type of tourism must be more attractive to tourists than beaches and natural resources. Pleasure, relaxation, fun experiences (X. Sun, Wang, Zhou, Wang, & Li, 2024), and enjoying nature (Humagain & Singleton, 2021) are the primary motivations for tourists to travel. This motivation differs significantly from heritage tourists, who are more driven by education and emotion (Prayag, Alrawadieh, & Alrawadieh, 2021). Hosseini Stefaniec, & Hosseini (2021) noted that tourists are not interested in cultural heritage for several reasons, including lack of awareness and interest, accessibility issues and limited tourism infrastructure, and overcrowding and over-tourism, which could be a negative experience.

However, on the contrary, developing cultural heritage to increase tourist visits often faces negative impacts. Several negative impacts of the development of cultural tourism often occur; first, the destruction of the socio-cultural order due to changes in lifestyle (Alamineh, Hussein, Endaweke, & Tadesse, 2023; Liu, Wang, Dupre, & McIlwaine, 2022), causing loss of identity and even social disruption (Al shawabkeh et al., 2023; Hosseini et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022) Apart from that, the commodification of culture for the sake of interests. Commercial and loss of cultural authenticity due to market demand (Al shawabkeh et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022; Tamakloe, 2011) is another severe problem. Paiva's (2023) research says that the tourism atmosphere influences the creation of tourists' feelings and experiences. The atmosphere results from social and environmental practices that develop over time in a place, providing unity in the perception of different spaces and influencing how people feel and connect with that place. It helps shape the unique identity of a place, culture, and community, creating a distinctive sense of uniqueness (Pink & Leder Mackley, 2016). Interest in the atmosphere of tourist attractions often impacts the authenticity of the place itself (Paiva, 2023). Tourists consider the atmosphere in remote places to be the most authentic. Imaginations of exotic 'others' are deeply ingrained in the minds of many tourists, often shaped by Western education, Orientalist novels, and contemporary media (Salazar & Grabum, 2016). The artificial atmosphere often leads to the view that tourism is intrusive among destination communities (Bell, 2015).

When indigenous culture is made into a commodity object in the tourism industry, significant challenges to its authenticity arise. This commodification process can damage or even change the true essence of the culture for commercial gain (Al shawabkeh et al., 2023; Ye, Xiao, & Zhou, 2018). Cultural artifacts may be standardized to fit a specific mold to meet the expectations of tourists seeking familiar experiences, potentially diluting their uniqueness and traditional value. This standardization can erode the authenticity of the artifacts (Tamakloe, 2011). Traditions that were once meaningful and sacred can be commercialized in the tourism industry, diminishing their spiritual and cultural significance. As a result, cultural and historical narratives can be distorted (Fan, Chang, & Ng, 2020).

Cultural heritage refers to the legacy of physical artifacts, intangible attributes, traditions, and values inherited from past generations and preserved for future generations. Tangible Cultural Heritage includes physical artifacts such as buildings, monuments, archaeological sites, works of art, and objects with cultural, historical, architectural, or artistic significance. Intangible Cultural Heritage includes traditions, rituals, performing arts, oral traditions, social practices, knowledge systems, and craftsmanship skills that are passed down from generation to generation and contribute to a community's cultural identity. Cultural heritage can also intersect with natural heritage, which includes natural landscapes, biodiversity, and ecosystems that have cultural significance or are related to human activities and traditions (Caust & Vecco, 2017; Wang, Zhang, & Qiu, 2022) Thus, cultural heritage tourism involves the use of historical resources and is the backbone of the tourism economy in many destinations. Cultural heritage tourism is a form of tourism that is deeply rooted in cultural heritage and aims to provide visitors with experiences that connect them with the past and foster a sense of identity, stewardship, and empowerment (Timothy, 2018).

Cultural heritage sites offer immersive experiences that connect visitors with the past through historical meaning through storytelling, architectural beauty, and cultural diversity through sensory experiences. Song, Moon, & Choe (2024) also explained that cultural heritage tourism offers sensory and physical experiences through cultural immersion. Cultural heritage destinations allow visitors to immerse themselves in local culture, traditions, and ways of life. These immersive experiences allow visitors to gain a deeper understanding of the heritage and values of a particular community. Authentic experiences at this site create a sense of identity and invaluable educational value while awakening a spiritual and emotional connection between tourists and local culture (Liu et al., 2022; Song et al., 2024; S. Zhang et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2024). Involving local communities, cultural heritage sites also provide platforms for meaningful cultural exchange, making them attractive destinations for tourists seeking a deep connection with a place (S. Zhang et al., 2023).

The presence of cultural heritage as part of a tour package often gives rise to debates regarding cultural authentication and identity. Some academics believe that cultural heritage tourism can strengthen cultural identity internationally. Heritage tourism can strengthen local identity by showcasing and celebrating a community's cultural traditions, history, and unique values. By promoting and preserving local heritage sites, traditions, and practices, cultural tourism can help residents feel a sense of pride and connection to their heritage (Koufodontis & Gaki, 2022; Park, 2010; Yanan, Ismail, & Aminuddin, 2024). Cultural heritage tourism experiences can also encourage social solidarity and influence how individuals view their cultural heritage and identity (Canale, De Simone, Di Maio, & Parenti, 2019; Timothy, 2018; Zou, Yang, Li, Liao, & Xiao, 2023). Tourism facilitates cultural exchange and dialogue between visitors and local communities, fostering mutual

understanding and appreciation of diverse cultures ((Yanan et al., 2024; S. Zhang et al., 2023). UNESCO's recognition of cultural heritage is not only an appreciation for cultural heritage but also promoting preservation efforts, raising awareness about the importance of preserving cultural and natural heritage, engaging local communities in tourism activities, and increasing visibility among tourists interested in visiting renowned heritage locations (Canale et al., 2019; Hosseini et al., 2021; S. Zhang et al., 2023).

However, the presence of tourists who want to enjoy the original culture of local communities can threaten the authenticity of local culture and identity. Tourists' desire to enjoy the authenticity of local culture by seeking authentic experiences encourages the development of artificial atmospheres by countries or companies for the benefit of tourism (Paiva, 2023). Liu et al. (2022) and Park (2010) indicate that commercial commodification is very dangerous for local identity. To meet tourist expectations, cultural performances, and displays may be staged or altered to fit stereotypes or misconceptions about culture, presenting an inauthentic or sanitized version of local traditions. This situation can distort visitors' perceptions of the true cultural heritage of a destination (S. Zhang et al., 2023). In contrast to Canale et al. (2019), Caust & Vecco (2017) and Vu et al. (2024) they raised concerns about the impact of uncontrolled tourism on UNESCO-recognized sites. He stressed the need for a balance between conservation, sustainability, and development.

The negative impact of tourism development on several aspects of human life has encouraged many countries to practice sustainable tourism. As an ideal concept to encourage tourism while avoiding some negative impacts, sustainable tourism develops through several strategies. The main criticism of tourism development is its impact on the environment. Therefore, sustainable tourism mainly aims to reduce environmental impacts by implementing practices that reduce carbon footprint, conserve natural resources, protect biodiversity, and minimize pollution to preserve the environment for future generations (Han et al., 2023; Hu, Tang, Chen, & Li, 2024; Swarbooke, 2023). Sustainable tourism requires the use of eco-friendly transportation options and energy-efficient accommodations. It also promotes waste reduction, recycling, and proper waste disposal practices to minimize pollution and environmental degradation. It includes educational components that raise awareness about environmental issues, conservation practices, and protecting natural ecosystems among tourists and local communities (Liu et al., 2022). Zhao et al. (2024) added that sustainable tourism practices ensure the long-term viability of cultural heritage sites by balancing economic benefits with environmental and social considerations.

Sustainable tourism also ensures that tourism activities contribute to local economic development, create job opportunities for residents, support small businesses, and distribute economic benefits equitably among stakeholders (Li et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024). However, the presence of tourists who want to enjoy the original culture of local communities can threaten the authenticity of local culture and identity. Tourists' desire to enjoy the authenticity of local culture by seeking authentic experiences encourages the development of artificial atmospheres by countries or companies for the benefit of tourism (Paiva, 2023). To ensure that sustainable tourism does not harm the interests of the local people, community engagement becomes a significant factor. Sustainable tourism empowers local communities by providing opportunities to participate in tourism activities, showcase their cultural heritage, and gain economic benefits. This empowerment can create a sense of ownership and pride in local resources and traditions. Community-based tourism initiatives empower local communities to develop and manage tourism activities according to their wishes. By promoting homestays, local tours, cultural performances, and artisan workshops, communities can benefit from tourism while preserving their way of life and traditions (Han et al., 2023; Li et al., 2024). Community-based tourism also emphasizes local control and participation in tourism enterprises. Ensure that the community members are actively involved in decision-making processes, planning, and implementation of tourism activities (Esteban), including involving local communities in conservation efforts to protect the natural environment because communities become managers of their land and resources (Liu et al., 2022).

Sustainable tourism also ensures community empowerment in tourism management and raises education and awareness. Encouraging local entrepreneurship by providing access to resources, funding, and market opportunities for small businesses and cooperatives aims to create diverse economic opportunities and diversify community incomes (Ruiz-Ballesteros & González-Portillo, 2024). In addition, training and skills development for residents in the tourism sector, such as hospitality, tour guides, handicrafts, and sustainable resource management, can help residents develop the skills and knowledge necessary to build and manage their tourism-related businesses effectively (Aquino, Schänzel, & Lück, 2018). Efforts are also being made to increase public awareness of the importance of sustainable tourism practices, environmental conservation, and cultural heritage, hoping that education will empower them to play an active role in sustainable tourism initiatives (Zhao et al., 2024). Community empowerment also develops knowledge and awareness of responsibility in

preserving tourist attractions. Not only for the community but responsibility is also borne by tourists and stakeholders involved in the tourism business (Han et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2022; Swarbooke, 2023).

Hu et al. (2024) underlined efforts to establish a regulatory framework for sustainable tourism. However, effective local, national, and international policies, regulations, and standards are essential in encouraging sustainable tourism practices and holding stakeholders accountable for their actions. Inadequate planning and regulations and ineffective law enforcement mechanisms can contribute to the success of sustainable tourism initiatives (Vu et al., 2024). Weak regulations and enforcement will not guarantee that sustainable tourism can protect the environment well enough from pollution, waste, and other environmental damage (Sarah). Weak regulations and enforcement will also not be able to guarantee access to policy-making to guarantee the welfare of their rights as owners of land and culture (Fernandez-Abila et al., 2024).

Overtourism due to interest in tourist destinations also often harms nature reserves and the environment (Al shawabkeh et al., 2023; Caust & Vecco, 2017; Liu et al., 2022). Overcrowding of tourists can cause damage to structures, erosion of fine features, and a reduction in the site's overall authenticity and historical value. It is not uncommon for tourists to also vandalize and damage cultural artifacts (Al shawabkeh et al., 2023). Environmental degradation also occurs when tourists are not well controlled, and pollution and piles of rubbish become unavoidable (Caust & Vecco, 2017). Overtourism can even result in habitat destruction and pressure on natural resources, impacting the ecological balance in that location (Hosseini et al., 2021). Additionally, pressure on infrastructure due to the influx of tourists can strain local infrastructure and facilities, leading to increased demand for resources such as air, waste management, transport, and accommodation (Al shawabkeh et al., 2023) as well as widespread environmental impacts (Liu et al., 2022).

Sustainable tourism is a concept that aims to minimize the negative impact of tourism on the environment, society, and economy while maximizing benefits for local communities and preserving cultural heritage and natural resources for future generations. Sustainable tourism seeks to balance meeting the needs of tourists and host communities, protecting the environment, and ensuring long-term economic viability (Han, Ramkissoon, You, & Kim, 2023; Li, Liu, & Solangi, 2024; Schönherr, Peters, & Kuščer, 2023; Zhao, Elahi, Wang, Xing, & Khalid, 2024). How can sustainable development encourage cultural heritage to become an attractive tourist destination that can provide economic benefits while protecting it from the negative impacts of tourism, especially from the erosion of cultural authenticity and commodification?

In practice, sustainable tourism must face several challenges. Hall (2011) notes that several governments must still integrate biodiversity values into economic policy. As a result, biodiversity continues to be threatened, with tourism's contribution to environmental change exceeding existing sustainability standards. Additionally, the gap between sustainable tourism goals and their actual impacts, known as the implementation gap, continues to hinder efforts for necessary changes in the sustainable development paradigm (Hall, 2011; Jeong, Karimov, Sobirov, Saidmamatov, & Marty, 2023; Vu, Vo-Thanh, Nguyen, Bui, & Pham, 2024). Apart from the gap between planning and implementation and neglect of environmental impacts, (Swarbooke, 2023; Vu et al., 2024) also noted that sustainable tourism failed to change tourist behavior due to a top-down approach and minimal involvement of stakeholders. Sustainable tourism is also unaware of the impact of seasonal labor challenges, the need for rewards in the form of investment in sustainable tourism businesses, and the need for education for tourism business actors.

When discussing the challenges of tourism development and its potential negative impacts on society, tourist attractions, and the environment, it is crucial to rely on factual sources. This article demonstrates how sustainable tourism can play a pivotal role in developing cultural heritage without compromising social order and cultural values. Our research, conducted using qualitative methods with a library research approach, draws on factual sources from books, journal articles, and existing proceedings, ensuring the reliability of our information.

Bibliometric analysis is used to obtain various scientific outputs from examining publications in specific fields or academic journals with the help of numerical and statistical analysis of several bibliometric indicators. Bibliometric analysis allows a systematic and comprehensive understanding of the de facto structure of any field, the nuances of the field's evolution, identifying the research groups that make up the field, capturing emerging trends, and gaining a broad perspective on the concepts that form the basis of the research (Öztürk, Kocaman, & Kanbach, 2024).

2. Method

This research has explored several data sources through the Scopus database regarding cultural heritage tourism in sustainable tourism. This research uses a qualitative method (Creswell & Creswell, 2018) with a literature study by collecting and observing data from library sources in journal articles, books, proceedings, etc. (Mardalis, 1999; Sugiyono, 2017). Data mining was carried out via Scopus. Over the years, Scopus has earned its equal place as a comprehensive bibliographic data source, and it has proven itself to be reliable and, in some respects, even better than WoS (Pranckutė, 2021). This research examines and reconstructs previous research by analyzing keywords to identify the most searched or interested subjects. The following keywords are used in searching data on the Scopus database engine, including "Cultural Heritage" and "Sustainable Tourism." Documents are selected based on the categories of research articles, book chapters, and proceedings, and then articles with vulnerabilities in the last seven years, namely 2018 to 2024, are determined. The data search results will indicate that the article is multidisciplinary and has achieved the highest number of citations by the first author (Chen, Qiu, Arsenault, & Larivière, 2021), as shown in Table 1. The following is a flowchart scheme for data collection from the Scopus database. Data analysis was conducted using the VOSviewer and NVivo 14 plus analysis tools. VOSviewer helps display bibliometric trends in studies on sustainable tourism in managing cultural heritage, increasing transparency in the research process (Waltman, van Eck, & Noyons, 2010). On the other hand, NVivo 14 utilizes the automatic coding feature to identify clusters and relationships and map themes related to sustainable tourism in managing cultural heritage. The search feature in NVivo empowers researchers to investigate their data at a specific level, potentially increasing the rigor of analysis by confirming or challenging researchers' initial perceptions. However, the usefulness of this software is reduced when assessing the validity and reliability of the thematic concepts that emerge during analysis, mainly due to the dynamic and inventive nature of the themes that emerge (Welsh, 2002).

Figure 1: Data Collection and Analysis Flowchart

Source: Processed by Author

3. Results

3.1. Cultural Heritage Management in Sustainable Tourism

This research has several variations in presenting data from 335 journal articles obtained by the author through a literature review of the Scopus database, including data representation based on keywords, affiliation, and presentation of research topic clusters with the last seven vulnerabilities—years from 2018 to 2024 and other data visualizations based on VOSviewer and NVivo 14 tools analysis. Table 1 depicts the ten authors with the most document citations. Szromek, Herman, & Naramski (2021) have the highest number of citations, namely 41 of all documents with an article entitled Sustainable Development of Industrial Heritage Tourism – A Case Study Development of the Industrial Monuments Route in Poland. Second is the article by Álvarez-García, Durán-Sánchez, & del Río-Rama (2018) entitled Scientific Coverage in Community-Based Tourism: Sustainable Tourism and Strategy for Social Development 39 citations. The third place is Trišić, Štetić, Privitera, & Nedelcu (2020) with the title Wine Routes in Vojvodina Province, Northern Serbia: A Tool for Sustainable Tourism Development with 34 citations. Moreover, next, there is Y. Sun, Timothy, Wang, Min, & Su (2019), with an article entitled Reflections on Agricultural Heritage Systems and Tourism in China, with 21 citations. Sangchumngong (2019) is in fifth place with an article entitled Development of a Sustainable Tourist Destination Based on the Creative Economy: A Case Study of Klong Kone Mangrove Community, Thailand. The article has 19 citations. In sixth place is Štetić, Trišić, & Nedelcu (2019), with an article entitled Natural Potentials of Significance for The Sustainable Tourism Development - The Focus on The Special Nature Reserve, which has 15 citations. The details can be seen in the visual Table 1.

Table 1: Authors with the Highest Citations

No.	Author	Title	Cited
1	Szromek et al. (2021)	Sustainable development of industrial heritage tourism – A case study of the Industrial Monuments Route in Poland	41
2	Álvarez-García et al. (2018)	Scientific Coverage in Community-Based Tourism: Sustainable Tourism and Strategy for Social Development	39
3	Trišić et al. (2020)	Wine Routes in Vojvodina Province, Northern Serbia: A Tool for Sustainable Tourism Development	34
4	Y. Sun et al. (2019)	Reflections on Agricultural Heritage Systems and Tourism in China	21
5	Sangchumnong (2019)	Development of a sustainable tourist destination based on the creative economy: A case study of Klong Kone mangrove community, Thailand	19
6	Štetić et al. (2019)	Natural Potentials of Significance for The Sustainable Tourism Development - The Focus on The Special Nature Reserve	15
7	Nechita, Demeter, Briciu, Varelas, & Kavoura (2019)	Projected Destination Images Versus Visitor-Generated Visual Content in Brasov, Transylvania	15
8	Kostopoulou, Sofianou, & Tsiokanos (2021)	Silk Road Heritage Branding and Polycentric Tourism Development	11
9	Vojnović (2018)	Tourist intensity in Croatia's leading tourist towns and municipalities	7
10	Žibert, Rozman, Škraba, & Prevorsek (2020)	A system dynamics approach to decision making tools in farm tourism development	6

Source: Scopus Data Analysis

Figure 2 shows the author affiliation where readers can find which institutions publish articles related to cultural heritage and sustainable tourism. The tabulation diagram in Figure 2 shows that from 2018 to 2024, the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and Universidad de Extremadura had the highest number of published documents compared to other affiliates, as evidenced by eight published papers. The second most published publications, with six papers each, are the University of Belgrade and the Faculty of Belgrade, University of Belgrade. The third positions with five papers from 2018-2014 are Universita degli Studi di Firenze, Politecnico di Milano, and Universidade de Aveiro. The last position has four documents: the University of Ferrara, the University of Johannesburg, and the Balkan Network of Tourism Experts.

Figure 2: Document by Affiliation

Source: Scopus Data Analysis

Visually, Figure 3 shows that ten countries have contributed to developing the topic of cultural heritage in sustainable tourism. Italy dominates nine other countries with 49 documents from 2018 to 2024. Meanwhile, Greece is second with 25 documents regarding sustainable tourism and cultural heritage. Figure 3 also shows that Spain made quite an enormous

contribution in the last seven years with 24 documents. China has contributed 22 papers in 7 years. The next position is Portugal with 21 documents, Turkey with 16 documents, and Poland and India with 15 documents. In ninth place is Indonesia, which also contributed ideas on the issue of cultural heritage in sustainable tourism with 12 documents in 7 years. The last position is in England, which has ten documents. It can be seen from the table that southern European countries have the most considerable contribution to related topics, considering that they are the most prominent tourism destination countries in Europe (Eurostat Statistic Explained, 2022) – Europe itself is the largest source of tourists (UNWTO processed by Our World in Data, 2023).

Figure 3: Document by Country

Source: Scopus Data Analysis

3.2. The Network between the Keyword “Cultural Heritage in Sustainable Tourism”

The inter-topic network is visualized as a network of keywords between issues that are relevant to each other and a network between topics. Keywords in inter-topic networks also have strength values in each network. Figure 4, with 335 articles from the Scopus database from 2018-2024, shows the analysis results via the VOSviewer network, which produces relationships between key terms. In the VOSviewer view below, lines connect different terms, and link strength indicates the number of publications in which two terms appear together; thicker lines indicate more robust relationships. VOSviewer determines that items are closely related when the software calculates the strength of association between similar items (Kirby, 2023). Figure 4 also explains each circle, representing keywords or words frequently appearing in the visual topic network. Nodes, typically depicted as circles, stand for significant publications, journals, researchers, or keywords, while edges, or connections, illustrate the associations between pairs of nodes. The proximity between the two nodes indicates the intensity of their relationship. Within network frameworks, distance is a gauge of the proximity and significance of the elements they signify (van Eck & Waltman, 2010).

Bibliometric analysis helps researchers and institutions assess scientific work's productivity, impact, and influence, identify emerging trends, and make informed decisions in research evaluation and strategic planning. Topic network visualizations use diverse visual elements to depict different aspects of data. VOSviewer is used for data exploration, mapping, and grouping retrieved articles. Keywords and countries are marked with colored circles. Circle size is positively correlated with the appearance of keywords or countries in the title and abstract. Therefore, the weight of a topic determines the size of its mark and circle. The greater the weight of a topic, the larger its label and circle (Wibowo & Adriani Salim, n.d.).

For comparison, each node in the cluster shows insights about bibliometric clustering. However, the size of the nodes in the bibliometric visualization of cultural heritage is slightly different. Sustainable Tourism Practices are in the same cluster as Cultural Heritage Preservation, Community Participation, Government, and Heritage Conservation. The small node of community participation shows that this issue has not received a place in international discussions about sustainable tourism. However, the role of government in heritage conservation and cultural heritage preservation is in the spotlight. Unfortunately, the tourism industry and economic growth are not in the same cluster. The visual network means that cultural heritage is still outside the scope of the tourism industry

(Ahmed, 2023; Alamineh et al., 2023; Groizard & Santana-Gallego, 2018). Moreover, the UNESCO node is in the same cluster as the tourism industry and economic growth. Meanwhile, Cultural Heritage Sites, Heritage Tourism, and Cultural Heritage Tourism must have close enough links with UNESCO and Cultural Heritage Preservation.

VOSviewer analytics involves analyzing keywords in the same thematic group through co-occurrence analysis. In VOSviewer, co-occurrence analysis focuses on identifying relationships based on the frequency of appearance of items within the same context. This analysis helps identify prominent relationships between keywords and visualize the interconnectedness among items through network maps. By clustering keywords that co-occur frequently, VOSviewer can create thematic groups or communities of terms within a text network. These thematic groups represent clusters of keywords closely related to the text data, providing insights into the underlying themes or topics present in the dataset (Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, Pandey, & Lim, 2021).

Figure 4: Bibliometric Analysis of the Keywords in Publication of Sustainable Tourism and Cultural Heritage. Co-occurrence of Keywords.

Source: Processed by Author using VOSviewer

Table 2: Cluster Topic “Cultural Heritage” AND “Sustainable Tourism”

Cluster 1	Red	Cultural Heritage Preservation, Community Participation, Government, Heritage Conservation, Sustainable Tourism Practices.
Cluster 2	Green	Economic Growth, Intangible Cultural Heritage, Tourism Industry, UNESCO
Cluster 3	Blue	Cultural Heritage Site, Heritage Tourism, Cultural Heritage Tourism

Source: Processed by Author using VOSviewer

Furthermore, VOSviewer's co-occurrence maps serve as a valuable starting point to identify relationships between items, such as keywords, and offer a high-level overview of the interconnectedness among items. By visualizing the co-occurrence of keywords in network maps, researchers can better understand the relationships and thematic connections present in the text data. This approach allows for the identification of key themes, topics, or clusters of related keywords, enabling researchers to explore and analyze the textual data more effectively (Bukar et al., 2023).

The visual network displayed in Figure 4 reveals three clusters, represented as red (Cluster 1), green (Cluster 2), and blue (Cluster 3) as outlined in Table 2. In the first cluster, there are no pretty dominant nodes. Cluster 1, marked by red nodes, includes cultural heritage preservation, sustainable tourism practices, and government and heritage conservation. Community participation issues - part of this cluster - are represented by smaller nodes. The cluster shows that community participation has yet to become widely discussed in government policies regarding cultural heritage preservation and sustainable tourism practices. The government's attention regarding cultural heritage preservation is still limited to policy and governance instruments.

Meanwhile, the biggest challenge comes from local governments, which prioritize economic growth and tourism revenue over the conservation of cultural heritage sites (Nurhadi, Sumarti, Hadi Dharmawan, & S Damanhuri, 2022; X. Zhang, Edelenbos, & Gianoli, 2024) or commercialization (Alexandrakis, Manasakis, & Kampanis,

2019; Melis, Wise, & Badurina, 2022). Štetić et al. (2019), Szromek et al. (2021) and I Trišić, Štetić, Maksin, & Blešić (2021) researchs show that sustainable tourism plays an essential role in preserving and promoting tourism. Cultural preservation is carried out by integrating ethno-social motifs and cultural traditions into tourism planning and development by creating unique experiences for visitors.

Even though the community participation node is small in the first cluster (even Trišić et al., 2020) and Štetić et al. (2019) do not mention it explicitly in the issue of sustainable tourism), several academics mention the critical role of community participation in sustainable tourism because community participation is essential for successful revitalization and preservation of industrial heritage, as it helps to prioritize projects based on the needs and interests of the local population (Alexandrakis et al., 2019; Szromek et al., 2021).

Community-based tourism (CBT) empowers underdeveloped regions by allowing local communities to develop tourism destinations, generating wealth and complementing their primary activities. CBT relies on local participation, equitable benefit distribution, resource preservation, successful support networks, local ownership, effective management, stakeholder communication, quality of life improvements, appropriate development scale, and tourist satisfaction (Ruiz-Ballesteros & González-Portillo, 2024; Sangchumnon, 2019)). More than that, sustainable tourism involving local communities in decision-making processes, planning, and implementation is crucial for ensuring that tourism benefits are distributed equitably and that negative impacts are minimized (Han et al., 2023; Swarbooke, 2023; Vu et al., 2024).

The second cluster includes Economic Growth, Intangible Cultural Heritage, Tourism Industry, and UNESCO themes. This cluster is quite interesting because UNESCO's recognition of heritage culture is a goal of many countries. UNESCO has recognized 933 cultures from all over the world (Unesco, 2024). UNESCO recognition is believed to make a positive contribution to tourism development and provide economic benefits because The UNESCO designation attracts attention from the media, tourists, donors, and decision-makers, enhancing the visibility of the cultural heritage site (Bertacchini, Revelli, & Zotti, 2024; Koufodontis & Gaki, 2022; McCarthy et al., 2022; Su & Lin, 2014). Apart from being a source of pride, this recognition also contributes as a medium for education on traditional values, historical values, and cultural practices, as well as being an encouragement for preservation and conservation efforts (Koufodontis & Gaki, 2022; McCarthy et al., 2022; Su & Lin, 2014).

However, Canale et al. (2019) and Caust & Vecco (2017) underscore the nuanced nature of UNESCO's recognition of intangible or tangible cultural heritage, cautioning that it does not always provide a straightforward positive contribution to cultural heritage itself. Cellini's econometric evaluation findings, for instance, reveal a surprising lack of positive correlation between UNESCO recognition and tourist arrivals. Spatial Analysis, as argued by Cuccia, Guccio, & Rizzo (2017), further supports this view, suggesting that UNESCO inscriptions themselves may not be as effective in encouraging cultural tourism or addressing seasonal tourists as previously thought. The research also uncovers a potential downside, indicating that cultural riches listed on the World Heritage List may harm the efficiency of tourism destinations. This multifaceted debate is crucial in understanding the intricate relationship between tourism, sustainable planning, and heritage conservation.

Setting aside the debate about UNESCO's influence on cultural tourism, it's important to note that the tourism industry demonstrates a statistically significant positive correlation with economic growth (Cannonier & Burke, 2019; Scarlett, 2021). The impact of this industry is far-reaching, manifesting in the form of expanding employment opportunities in various sectors such as hotels, accommodations, transportation, finance, insurance, and entertainment (Kadriu, 2016). It also generates income in the form of foreign exchange and taxes for the government, attracts investment (Lohana, Imran, Harouache, Sadia, & Ur Rehman, 2023; Singh & Alam, 2024), and stimulates infrastructure and small-scale business development. These findings paint a promising picture of the tourism industry's potential to drive economic prosperity.

The third cluster refers to cultural heritage sites, heritage tourism, and cultural heritage tourism. These nodes are closely related because heritage sites and cultural heritage tourism are part of heritage tourism objects. This cluster is close to specific nodes from other clusters, such as UNESCO nodes, cultural heritage preservation, tourism industry, and community participation. As discussed, UNESCO's recognition has contributed to cultural heritage

The words 'sustainable' and 'conservation' are words that often appear because, in discussions about sustainable tourism, conservation is a keyword for maintaining and protecting cultural heritage from the onslaught of the tourism industry, which is more concerned with economic profits alone (Aquino et al., 2018; Ghasemi, González-García, Charrahy, & Serrao-Neumann, 2024; Schönherr et al., 2023). The main idea of the concept of sustainable tourism refers to how to increase economic benefits from tourism without causing negative impacts on the environment, cultural values, and cultural artifacts. The most important thing is not to displace local communities.

In line with the findings in the VOSviewer visualization, the word 'community' also emerged as an important issue in discussions about cultural heritage in sustainable development. The word 'community' is often related to the word 'participant,' meaning that community participants are crucial to sustainable tourism. Apart from being guardians of cultural identity and their environment (Liu et al., 2022; Mmeko, Molosi-France, & Dipholo, 2023; Yanan et al., 2024), communities must also be included in decision-making so that they are not marginalized in tourism industry practices (Beal, Séraphin, Modica, Pilato, & Platania, 2019; Mmeko et al., 2023). Empowering local communities is very important so that they have sufficient capability and knowledge to make policies (Mmeko et al., 2023; Moayerian, McGehee, & Stephenson, 2022; Rachmawati, 2020; Žibert et al., 2020).

4. Conclusion

Research on cultural heritage in sustainable tourism has been undertaken over the last seven years. From 2018 to 2024, 335 journal articles were obtained from the Scopus database. Through analysis of the VOSviewer tool, it was found that the institutions that contributed the most to research on cultural heritage and sustainable tourism were the University of Thessaloniki and Universidad de Extremadura. Thus, the countries that made the most significant contribution were Italy and Greece. Meanwhile, the first three authors with the most quotations are Álvarez-García et al. (2018), Szromek et al. (2021) and Igor Trišić et al. (2020).

UNESCO's recognition of cultural heritage is one of the recognitions sought by countries because this recognition not only encourages the tourism industry but also increases economic growth due to tourist arrivals. However, the negative impact of commercialization and cultural commodification due to over-tourism is a deep concern. Sustainable tourism is the middle ground for developing an economically oriented tourism industry. However, it also reduces negative impacts on the environment, cultural and traditional values, artistic artifacts, and caring for local communities.

Cultural heritage is not just a tourism commodity. It is the cultural identity of local people and the identity of a nation. Therefore, cultural heritage tourism must include cultural preservation and conservation to maintain cultural values and avoid damage to cultural artifacts. Thus, Sustainable tourism places cultural heritage not only to utilize the potential of cultural heritage as a cultural heritage tourism product but also as an effort to protect cultural identity and maintain cultural heritage.

Author Contributions: All authors contributed to this research.

Funding: Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

Acknowledgments: A number of institutions provided considerable funding for the execution of this research. The financial support from the Directorate General of Research and Development Reinforcement, Ministry of Research, Technology, and Higher Education of the Republic of Indonesia, proved crucial in enabling this study in 2024, for which we express our gratitude. We would want to express our heartfelt gratitude to the Institute for Research and Community Service at Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Yogyakarta, Indonesia, for their invaluable assistance in handling the administrative aspects of this scientific project.

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